

Pathogen genomics data sharing: public health meets research

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Introduction

This piece is intended to inform the discussion around pathogen genomics data sharing and the principles under which sharing occurs.

The era of pathogen genome sequencing

As reliability, availability and cost have fallen over the last two decades, whole genome sequencing has grown from specialist scientific research tool in the hands of an expert few to mainstream method available to many that can be applied en masse and routinely across broad dimensions of pathogen study.

The popularity of sequencing reflects a host of benefits that it brings; sequencing is highly versatile in that it can be applied in different ways to answer many different questions about a given pathogen; it is universal, in that as a single technology it can be applied across all pathogens; it frequently yields results more rapidly than alternative methods, in large part because it avoids growth-based steps that are required for many traditional typing and resistance profiling methods; it is increasingly anonymous, especially as metagenomics methods advance, in that one needs little or no knowledge of which pathogen is in a sample to initiate sequencing; it provides depth and precision beyond alternative assays (e.g. typing at the level of the complete set of variations in a genome rather than individual positions or regions); it is pluripotent - data from a single sequencing assay can answer many different questions such as about evolution, spread, pathogenicity, resistance and pathogen biology; and finally sequencing not only provides an expedient alternative to traditional methods, but it also enables a wealth of new applications for which there is no existing method.

Whole genome pathogen sequencing is set to grow in importance and ubiquity in the study of pathogens.

The importance of data sharing

The interpretation of sequence data, perhaps in contrast to data from many other laboratory methods, is unusually dependent upon comparison and contrast with existing sequence data from other studies, other parts of the world and other scientists. While many methods require reference data sets for calibration and normalisation of results, the interpretation of sequence requires access not only to relatively static data sets, such as reference genomes and marker sets, but also in the case of pathogens to highly dynamic collections of sequences from surveillance, outbreak investigation, biological characterisation and many other diverse studies. Alone a sequence in isolation is typically uninformative; in order to make even a preliminary assessment, the sequence must be compared against sets of existing sequences, or analysed using tools that apply models built on these sets. To learn more a scientist will typically align to other sequences, build trees, compare coding regions, and much more. It is only through access to collections of sequences that knowledge can emerge; the more comprehensive the collection, the greater the potential for advance. Due to the pluripotent nature of sequence data, much value from data emerges through its reuse and not its initial use for the purposes under which it was generated; indeed, meta-analysis, repurposing studies and serendipitous discovery based on publicly available data provide an ongoing narrative in the life sciences.

For this reason, the research community, in which sequencing saw its early development and uptake, has for the last 40 years adopted a model of open data sharing through the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration¹. The model is necessarily open with as few restrictions in place as is possible. Any restriction results in friction in discovery, access and use which serves to impede collective advance. Because the data can be redistributed, decomposed, mixed and transformed, not only have successive generations of scientists directly benefited from the corpus of shared open data, but databases, computational processes and curation programmes have also accessed, added expert value, curated alongside the literature and vastly amplified the value of the shared sequence data in an ecosystem of databases, themselves open and interconnected. It is estimated that more than 1,000 databases exist in this ecosystem that in some way draw upon and add value to openly shared genomics data².

Public health meets research

The responsibilities of the infectious disease public health community span surveillance work, risk analysis and targeted sampling, outbreak investigation, origin and zoonosis identification, endemic and pandemic-tracking and the monitoring of selection and evolution of pathogen genomes with potential to impact response to therapies and vaccines. Each of these complex workflows generates and consumes sequence data.

The research community in infectious disease also has a breadth of functions. However, these can typically not be defined in advance as is possible for those of public health; while one can classify some workflows, such as drug discovery and vaccine development, for much of research the research community, questions into such areas as pathogen biology,

¹ Arita *et al.* 2020; <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/33166387>

² Rohden *et al.* 2019; <https://www.cbd.int/abs/DSI-peer/Study-Traceability-databases.pdf>

host interaction and drug resistance mechanisms are by nature more open-ended and led by curiosity more than by application. As for public health, research workflows both generate and consume sequence data.

As sequencing becomes an increasingly important platform that is shared by public health and research workflows, the two communities become necessarily - and fruitfully - more interdependent. The data generated in a public health workflow can be repurposed for use in a research study, for example a set of surveillance sequences can indicate sites of greater and more constrained variation, providing clues as to the importance of the given region for pathogen fitness. Similarly, research data, such as sequences from microbial diversity studies, will provide data for phylogenetics analyses in origin tracing. Complex flows of data and interpretation between the communities will become a key element for both public health and research.

Generating sequence around the world

Both public health investigators and researchers operate in institutional, regional and national contexts which have conventions, rules and laws about how data can and should be shared, and capacity coupled to priorities about the importance of this sharing. This context varies from country to country. In particular there are typically large differences between higher-income and lower-income countries. Higher-income countries nearly always have more capacity for their researchers to share data, with conventions, rules and laws which enable data sharing. Conventions include growing national recognition of the importance of data sharing as part of the scientific and public health agendas; rules include aspects of funding mandates for data sharing. Laws on data sharing have become more involved and complex, but ultimately provide legal routes for appropriate data sharing. In contrast, in lower-income countries the capacity and support for data sharing is often lower, with many other competing priorities facing individuals and organisations. Furthermore at times, conventions do not reward data sharing, focusing more on the recognition of other forms of contribution to science, such as scholarly publication. Coupled to these conventions, rules in institutions and laws can inhibit or explicitly ban data sharing, or provide loose legal rules which place considerable risk for data sharing on institutions or individuals. Finally national laws may explicitly reserve data sharing of certain data types on the basis of national priorities.

These differences in the context in which sequence is generated necessarily impact the mechanisms chosen for data sharing across borders. It is important to acknowledge the differences as they define what is possible and reasonable for individuals around the world. For example, as we lay out below, data sharing for public health purposes is most effective at global level and with full openness, but such data sharing might be considered too risky or as removing the benefits of unique datasets for national scientists in some countries.

A need to link data

For many applications, pathogen sequence data can only be interpreted when set in context broader than the immediate metadata carried in sequence records. Particularly powerful is the connection between pathogen sequence (and hence genotype and predicted phenotype)

and data relating to the pathogen's host (such as health status, vaccine exposure, antimicrobial treatment history and travel patterns); where this connection is precise - the very pathogen genome(s) carried by a host map to the very host individual that was infected - major insights can arise.

Data linking provides an approach that allows logical connections between pairs of sequences (such as between animal host and pathogen sequences within an open sequence database), between pathogen sequences and sensitive patient/research subject sequence data held in controlled access databases and between pathogen sequences and records across broad (open and controlled-access) data resources in the domains of epidemiology, health data, social sciences, economics and more.

Enabling linking requires openness in the data. In many cases, while remote data may be under controlled access, data links can be asserted openly that allow those accessing sequence records to discover and navigate towards linked records. In some cases, where donor consent limits even exposing that the remote data set exists, links must be asserted within the remote database and users of this system can follow links to navigate to pathogen sequence records. In either case, an open linking system based on tracking identifiers relating to patients and samples is required. In order to operate curatorial processes to assert links and, as is often required for analysis, to make available pathogen sequence alongside controlled access data in an appropriate analysis environment, it is also important that the pathogen sequence data can be replicated and propagated.

Urgency of sharing

The urgency with which sharing of pathogen sequence data must happen in order to satisfy different public health and research workflows varies. For certain applications, such as the identification of early signals of possible outbreaks from surveillance programmes, data sharing must be very rapid and as near as possible to real-time. In times of public health emergency, such as pandemic situations, for case-associated sequences with their capacity to identify variation, virulence and resistance characteristics, sharing is essential in real-time or as near as possible. In other cases, though, such as meta-analysis with a view to mechanistic studies into infectious mechanisms in a pathogen not currently circulating in high numbers or at high rates, there is lower urgency for sharing.

Data elements to be shared

Over time, and according to cases and circumstances, exactly which elements of pathogen sequence data and metadata should be shared varies. Data standards developed and maintained by the communities providing and consuming data - those stakeholders best placed to understand the constraints of provision and to balance the necessities of richness for analysis - have historically successfully guided scientific data sharing activities³. Thus, as public health and research meet, such communities are best placed to define and maintain the standards and best practices around shared pathogen genomics data.

³ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

Pathogen genomics data analysis and interpretation is an effort that brings together scientific and bioinformatics expertise. Typically, bioinformatics does not provide a singular and perfect analysis routine for a given sequencing-based assay, but offers a number of options, each perhaps focused on a particular question, which each operate based on their own sequencing error models; although two established assembly or variation-calling methods will typically provide strong similarity or overlap, outputs will also likely also differ to some extent. For this reason, the safest option is that sharing includes raw sequence read data to allow alternative analysis methods to be applied. For the current mainstream sequencing platforms raw data is read-level sequence and per-position quality scores, represented in unaligned (FASTQ) or genome-aligned formats (BAM or CRAM).

Providing immediate context through sequence metadata is a key element of a usefully shared pathogen sequence data set. Sequencing method, configuration of machine, primer information and other laboratory methods are important and often unquestioned elements to be shared. Minimally, spatio-temporal sample collection data - expressed if required with low precision or controlled obfuscation - is useful universally across pathogen samples. Data relating to the nature of the sampling (blood, swab, etc.) for a patient/research subject or sampled site (e.g. wastewater plant, hospital waiting room door knob) are commonly an important addition. Data relating to the circumstances of a patient or research subject, such as their age, sex and disease presentation/severity, are typically considered to be non-sensitive and of high value in the use of the shared sequence data. Beyond these elements, a system in which it is possible for data providers to report deeper contextual information will be beneficial, although greater depth often defines the transition into more sensitive data that must be held under controlled access and linked to pathogen sequence data.

Benefit sharing challenges

Data providers, their institutions and the countries and regions in which the institutions operate are critical elements of genomics-based public health and research activities. Their engagement in data sharing is fundamental to a globally comprehensive view of circulating pathogens, an understanding of their biology and pathways to contain their spread and impact.

In infectious disease, there are indisputable global inequalities in the extents to which different regions are affected by disease, are capable of appropriate outbreak response and have access to the necessary sanitary measures, therapeutics and vaccines. In the absence of political solutions to these inequities, the openness with which the research community traditionally shares sequence data is at times criticised as it is suspected by some that data sharing in itself may be a causal factor in inequity, where the drugs and vaccines, for example, are not accessible to those sharing their data. We argue, though, that given the acceleration that open sharing of data can give to our understanding and response to pathogens, as we have laid out above, open data sharing is an essential part of the solution to inequity in that without it, our options to respond are limited and the possibility of benefits from any genomics are so much more constrained.

A valued contribution from data-providing scientists

In many higher-income countries, public health agencies have mandates to generate surveillance and outbreak data and to provide these data as a service to public health. Beyond quality control and analysis sufficient to plan the appropriate response, there is typically little reason for these sequence data not to be publicly and openly shared very soon after generation; those generating the sequences and the countries in which they operate have access to the benefits that are derived from the global sequencing effort to which they have contributed.

The scientific output of researchers is typically assessed based upon their contributions to the scholarly literature. Importantly, many scientists working in public health have, alongside their institutions' surveillance sequencing activities, research functions in which they also generate research sequence data; these scientists are commonly also assessed on their literature output. Since early release of sequence data can give competing scientists an opportunity to analyse and publish before the generating scientist has had the chance, there is substantial use of the "hold until publication" mode within INSDC. Preparing the data for open release and referencing in the ultimate publication, such data sets remain private until publication is reached.

For pathogen sequence data in the cases of public health emergency, regardless of the basis for its generation (public health or research), release as early as possible becomes extremely important to allow progress at speed against the disease. For those in wealthier countries, institutions and funders expect and may support a redirection of efforts under emergency situations allowing researchers to release pathogen sequence data openly and early without damage to publication record. However, for some scientists in low-resource settings, the opportunities for others in higher-resource countries with greater capacity to move quickly are very real, and the fears of being "scooped" are barriers for rapid data sharing.

For data generated for the purposes of surveillance, then, early open sharing is expected. Under normal circumstances, data generated for research purposes will be beneficial to the advance of pathogen science if released as early as possible and no later than publication in the literature. Under circumstances of public health emergency, one would expect research data of relevance to be released immediately after generation and quality control. For those in low-resource settings under these emergency circumstances, research data sets should be shared with all but if necessary under conditions that temporarily disallow publication by others without owners' permission for a limited time period.

Across scientific disciplines, much emphasis is placed upon the outcomes and impacts of the scientific process. A reward system for academic scientists that is skewed towards scholarly publication, in which career advances and access to funding are dependent on publication records and scientists themselves often judge their peers by their publications, is pervasive. While communicating findings is of course important, this configuration of the profession has a tendency to underestimate the complexity of the scientific process and the scientific and technical expertise and effort of those who generate and share data. Such mechanisms as mandatory acknowledgement or co-authorship of data providers have been proposed, but in the world of multilateral and urgent pathogen sequence data sharing, these

are impractical, unscalable and antiquated. Rather, culture change around recognition of the value that is attached to data generation and provision is required to rebalance the views of employers, funders and scientific peers; such change will be aided by improved attribution tools that allow data providers better to profile and demonstrate their data contributions as part of their scientific output.

Bioinformatics capacity building

Access to sequence data - one's own and others' - is just a first step in leveraging the technology. Bioinformatics processes, which can be demanding on requirements for hardware, network, infrastructure and expertise are the essential next step in analysis and interpretation.

Those working in low and middle income countries are most hit by the scale of requirements. While many data sharing systems offer solutions in part, such as remote access to compute capacity and analysis tools, such offerings do not always provide the level of local control and ownership of the analysis and interpretation process that is required. Pathogen data sharing on a global scale requires an engaged global community in all reaches of the world. Investment in the building of capacity and fostering balanced collaboration will serve to share out the work required to master pathogen genomics data and build true engagement on equal terms.

Governance

All citizens and governments are the stakeholders in pathogen genomics data sharing as it is an instrument of public health and research. Appropriate governance must be in place: citizens and nations must be able - through some channel - to steer the system in order to maintain mission and to satisfy equitable access; decision making relating to design, direction, leadership and application of terms of use must be transparent to all; the protection of private data relating to individuals must be safeguarded; and the system must be available with equity for all.

Principles of data sharing

- Pathogen genomics data sharing is a shared interest and responsibility for public health and research communities
- Pathogen genomics data have the fullest value as a comprehensive set rather than as fragmented collections
- Open pathogen genomics data linking is required to provide context to pathogen genomics data
- All pathogen genomics data should be as open as possible as early as possible with the urgency of data sharing for different applications reflected in best practice
- Data standards should be developed and maintained by the scientific communities that provide and consume pathogen genomics data
- Open pathogen genomics data sharing is a foundation for a more equitable global approach to infectious disease
- Data generation and provision into the shared data set is a scientific and technical contribution invaluable to downstream outcomes and impacts
- Pathogen data sharing must take place under a governance framework of transparency, accountability and mutual benefit